

EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES ON COMPOSITE BONDED JOINTS

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SUMMARY: The double lap shear specimen is examined in detail to serve as a baseline for further research on the behavior of composite to composite adhesive bonded joints. Four laminate surface preparation techniques were examined in detail. The four are a simple acetone wash, hand sanding, surface grinding, and grit blasting. A comparison is made between the 3D stress analysis and the experiments using small strain gages placed in regions of high strain gradients. The results match well except in the region precisely at the corner of the adherends where stress singularities occur. The damage propagation modes were observed and characterized. Failure within the composite was the general mode of failure, resulting in final ultimate strengths which did not appear to be sensitive to the surface preparation method.

KEYWORDS: adhesive, bonding, failure modes, surface preparation, double lap joint, 3501-6, FM-300

INTRODUCTION

An understanding of the behavior of bonded joints has become increasingly important to the U. S. Air Force. This is primarily for two reasons: first, the use of composite materials in Air Force aircraft has been increasing dramatically over the past decade, and with the future introduction of aircraft with higher percentages of highly loaded primary composite structures, the need to repair these structures is critical. It is envisioned that many of the repairs will require adhesively bonded scarf joints. The second primary reason for the renewed interest in bonded structure is that many of the future concepts for low cost composite structures entail large, highly unitized structures, for which adhesively bonded joints may play a large role. For both of these applications, an understanding of the long-term performance of the joints under repeat mechanical and environmental (primarily moisture and temperature) loading is required.

The long range objective of the overall program, then, is to develop analysis methods for the accurate prediction of failure in composite bonded joints. It is envisioned that this effort will entail many components, including fully three dimensional stress analysis, testing and characterization of failure, the extension or development of 3D failure criteria necessary for the correlation between analysis and experiments, the understanding of cyclic moisture, temperature, and mechanical loading effects on failure in adhesively bonded composite joints, and, finally, the effects of 'real world' issues on bond failure, to include poor surface preparation, uneven curing of the bondline adhesive, and uneven bondline thickness. The

objective of the current study, however, is far more modest. It is to establish a baseline understanding of the failure modes of composite to composite adhesive bonds in the double lap shear specimen (the description of and rationale for selection will be given in the next section). Further studies will continue to explore the areas described above.

MATERIALS, SPECIMEN CONFIGURATION AND PREPARATION

The material chosen for the adherents was Hercules AS4/3501-6, considered a well characterized, commonly used carbon fiber reinforced brittle epoxy system. The adherent lay-ups were $[0]_{16T}$. The bonding adhesive chosen was Cytec FM300-2U (neat film) and FM300-2K (film with 3% woven glass scrim).

The specimen geometry is shown in Fig. 1. The specimens were fabricated in several steps: first, the adherent plates, measuring 30.5 cm x 30.5 cm (12" x 12") were cured following the manufacturer's instructions. Next, the bonding surfaces underwent one of four surface treatments: 1. acetone wash only, 2. moderate hand sanding with 240 grit sandpaper, followed by an acetone wash, 3. surface grinding with a 56 grit silicon carbide wheel to remove 0.05 mm (0.002") of the panel surface, followed by an acetone wash, and 4. grit blasting with 30 grit particles at 0.62 MPa (90 psi), also followed by an acetone wash. The film adhesive was then applied to the full sized plates; shim plates were added to prevent the adherents from bending during the application of external pressure, and the plates were placed in a hot press at 0.69 MPa (100 psi) to cure the adhesive. The adhesive cured according to the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle (Fig. 2) resulted in an unacceptable level of porosity and uneven bond quality, as shown by the C-scan results in Fig. 3. To remedy this, several steps were taken. The first was the addition of a temperature hold step, at the point of minimum resin viscosity, at a temperature slightly below the final cure temperature, as depicted in Fig. 4. It was believed the additional resin flow time would assist in allowing volatiles to escape from the adhesive. In addition, the plates were placed in an autoclave to apply the external pressure, also 0.69 MPa (100 psi). The results are shown in Fig. 5, and indicate significantly improved bondline quality. Once cured, the panels were cut into 2.54 cm (1") width specimens, after which strain gages (in locations to be discussed) and tabs were applied.

The results of the various surface preparation techniques are shown in Figures 6-9, which are low magnification views of the surfaces prior to bonding. In Fig. 6, the imprints of the woven peel ply texture in the surface of the laminate are apparent (recall that this laminate is unidirectional). Fig. 7 shows the effects of moderate hand sanding, where the peaks in the surface resin have been removed, however the low regions are unaffected. Fig. 8 illustrates the intermediate roughness created by the surface grinding, and Fig. 9 shows the highly roughened surface from the grit blasting. It should be noted that, also in this same sequence of surface preparation techniques, the surface roughness increases, as does the amount of fiber breakage and microcrack formation in the laminate. The extreme case is depicted in Fig. 10, which is a high resolution magnification of the damage caused by the grit blasting. The high surface roughness, broken fibers, resin splitting, and surface debris are apparent.

TEST RESULTS

Many of the specimens were instrumented with strain gages to monitor the surface strains at select locations. Back-to-back gages on both the single adherent section of the specimen, as

well as in the region of bond overlap, indicate by their nearly identical output that a high level of symmetry exists in the specimen. In addition, very small gages, 0.38 mm (0.015") in length, were located in regions on the specimen edges near the bond line. A sample output from a single set of such gages is given in Fig. 11. It is worth noting that gages 4 and 5 measure transverse strains, whereas gages 6 and 7 measure axial strains. Also, gages 4 and 6 are located just in the corner region of the adherent, whereas gages 5 and 7 are also located on the laminate, directly adjacent to the adhesive bond, but at a distance of 0.63 mm (0.25") from the end of the bondline. In this example, the specimen was loaded to a peak load approximately 30% of the load required to cause crack initiation, and approximately one fifth of the ultimate load. Even at this low load level, hysteresis can clearly be seen in the gage outputs at the crack tip.

Two dimensional [1] and a three dimensional [2] analytical solutions for stress and strain were developed for this configuration. The stress results for the 2D solution are presented in Fig. 12. The results clearly show the non-uniformity in shear stress along the length of the specimen, as well as the significant singular peel stress that develop at the ends of the bondline. In reality, the specimen has double free edges: the edges along the sides of the specimen, as well as the edges perpendicular to the longitudinal axis of the specimen. The strain gage output was compared with the 3D results, and the comparison is given in Table 1. It is clear that the corner strains vary significantly between specimens, as well as between specimens and the analytical solution. However, the strains 6.3 mm (0.25"), still fairly close to the crack tip, match the analytical solution fairly well. It should be noted that the results for the analytical solution were averaged over the gage area to provide a fair comparison.

Fig. 1: Configuration of the double lap shear specimen

Fig. 2: Temperature and viscosity profiles cycle of the Cytec FM-300 adhesive subjected to the standard processing cycle

Fig. 3: Ultrasonic C-scan of the FM-300 bonded plates cured in a hot press at 0.69 MPa using the standard cure cycle

Fig. 4: Temperature viscosity profiles cycle of the Cytec FM-300 adhesive subjected to the modified processing cycle

Fig. 5: Ultrasonic C-Scan of the FM-300 bonded plates cured in an autoclave at 0.69 MPa using the modified cure cycle

*Fig. 6: Surface of the laminate with acetone wash only.
Note the textile texture imprint from the peel ply*

Fig. 7: Surface of the laminate with moderate hand sanding

Fig. 8: Surface of the ground laminate before bonding

Fig. 9: Surface of the grit blasted laminate before bonding

Fig. 10: Close-up of the surface of the grit blasted laminate before bonding

Fig. 11: Output from the 0.38 mm (0.015") size strain gages located on the specimen adherent edges adjacent to the adhesive bondline

Fig. 12(a): Normalized (by the axial stress in the single adherend) shear stress at the bondline interface as a function of bondline position

Fig. 12(b): Normalized (by the axial stress in the single adherend) shear stress at the bondline interface as a function of bondline position

Table 1: Comparison of Experimental Strains and Analytical Predictions

CORNER STRAINS

	<u>EXP: DL2-2</u>	<u>EXP: DL3-1</u>	<u>ANALYTICAL</u>
ϵ_x/ϵ_{x0}	0.2458	0.1915	0.1070
ϵ_y/ϵ_{x0}	0.0500	0.2010	0.7740

NEAR CORNER STRAINS
0.25" INSET

	<u>EXP: DL2-2</u>	<u>EXP: DL3-1</u>	<u>ANALYTICAL</u>
ϵ_x/ϵ_{x0}	0.3933	0.3103	0.3529
ϵ_y/ϵ_{x0}	-0.1930	-0.1929	-0.1744

In order to observe the failure sequence, the edges of the specimens were polished prior to testing. Next, the specimens were loaded incrementally until crack initiation and propagation was observed. Fluorescent dye was applied to the polished edge while the specimens were still under load. The loading was then removed, and the specimens edges were observed under an optical microscope, illuminated by a fluorescent light source. The onset of crack initiation was also indicated by acoustic emission output. Failure in nearly all of the specimens followed a regular pattern, as depicted in Fig. 13. The cracks generally initiated in the region of maximum peel stress at 70% of the ultimate failure load. The cracks then propagated to approximately the midpoint of the specimen. A second crack, at the opposite side of the bondline, then forms within the specimen. These cracks then link via a third crack which traverses the bondline.

The cracks, when observed under the optical microscope, appeared to be located at the interface between the composite and the adherent. Upon careful examination under the scanning electron microscope, however, it was clearly observed that for all four surface preparation techniques, the failure was within the laminates themselves, just several fiber diameters from the laminate surface. This is illustrated in Fig. 14, which shows clearly the presence of fibers (as does the mating surface), indicating primary crack propagation within the laminate. In addition, as observed in the laminates before bonding, the number of broken fibers increased when examining the acetone washed only, the hand sanded, the ground, and the grit blasted specimens, respectively.

The ultimate failure loads are given in Table 2. It is felt that the variation in strength of the specimens is not significantly effected by the surface preparation method (the high failure value in the acetone wash specimen is based on only one test).

Fig. 13: Depiction of the damage initiation and growth as seen by fluorescent enhanced edge microscopy

Fig. 14: Typical image of the fracture surface showing intra-ply failure

Table 2. Ultimate failure load for four surface preparation techniques

	Failure Stress (Far Field in the Single Adherent) <u>MPa (ksi)</u>	<u>Number of Specimens</u>
Acetone wash	501 (72.7)	1
Hand sanding	439 (63.7)	3
Grinding	469 (68.0)	2
Grit blasting	453 (65.7)	3

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Several significant issues become apparent when examining the results. First, in the corner region of the specimen, potential viscoelastic effects may be present and must be accounted for in the stress analysis. In addition, the shape of the adhesive fillet was generally uncontrolled and may effect the stress state in that region.

The effect of surface preparation did not appear to have a significant effect on the specimen strength. This may not be surprising, as all failures were observed to occur within the composite, and hence the intra-ply strengths dictate the failure level. However, as future tests are conducted under more extreme moisture and temperature conditions, the failure modes may change.

Immediate future plans for this project include the use of full field moiré instead of strain gages to monitor strains in the regions of high strain gradients, the use of multi-directional laminates as adherents, and the testing of moisture conditioned specimens at cold, room, and elevated temperatures. An additional laminate and adhesive will also be added to the test matrix. Longer term plans include the addition of alternate test geometries to alter the stress state in the bond region.

In summary, the double lap shear specimen has been examined in detail to serve as a baseline for further research on the behavior of composite to composite adhesive bonded joints. Four laminate surface preparation techniques were examined in detail. A comparison was made between the 3D stress analysis and the experiments using small strain gages placed in regions of high strain gradients. The damage propagation modes were observed and characterized, and the final ultimate strengths reported and discussed with respect to them.

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